

Impact of Emerging Trends and Socio-Cultural Shifts on Modern Saudi Arabian Consumer Behavior

Mohammad Naquibur Rahman, Ph.D.
Associate Professor of Marketing
College of Business, Alasala
Saudi Arabia

Rawnaq Ara Parvin
Department of Sociology, Varendra University, Rajshahi-6204, Bangladesh

Md. Ashiqur Rahman
Department of Management Studies, Rajshahi University, Rajshahi-6205, Bangladesh

Abstract

This research examined the influence of social and cultural variables on shopping habits among Saudi Arabia's young, tech-savvy consumers—key drivers of the country's socio-economic transformation. Conducting a convenient survey among 212 individuals, factors such as trust, price sensitivity, social influences, convenience, and customer satisfaction were explored. Research findings reveal that trust in product authenticity and payment security significantly shapes purchasing decisions. Price concerns are paramount, with consumers prioritizing fair pricing and promotions. Socio-religious values, brand, and media influences are present, but their impact is relatively minor; they are overshadowed by trust and pricing concerns. Correlation analysis depicts strong positive relationships between trend awareness and factors including recognition of counterfeit brands (0.475), belief in extravagant consumption (0.452), and price sensitivity (0.439). Regression analysis shows that these predictors explain approximately 41.6% of the variation in trend awareness, with counterfeit brand awareness notably impacting consumer behavior (coefficient: 0.1983, p-value: 0.003). These insights weigh the necessity of ensuring product authenticity, competitive pricing, and high-quality customer service. Businesses can apply these findings by adapting marketing strategies that resonate with consumer preferences, such as promoting genuine products and offering flexible pricing options. Furthermore, this study aligns with the objectives of Saudi Vision 2030, advocating for an innovative and customer-centric marketplace that supports economic growth.

Keywords: New emerging trends, buying behavior, social influences, trust, price and convenience factor, Shopping and Convenience factor.

1. Introduction

Customer behavior and industry trends-related market research are essential for understanding a company's targeted markets and rivals. In the last four decades, Saudi Arabia experienced rapid and dramatic changes in socio-economic and political progress. Transforming to modernization the KSA has upgraded to a service economy sector from the traditional agricultural oil-based economy with a fast-paced consumer culture (Almutairi et al., 2023; Moshashai et al., 2020a; Samargandi et al., 2014; Yusuf, 2016). The Arabian market is dynamic and offers special opportunities and challenges. KSA's per capita income and GDP are formidable and increasing day by day. Saudi market is not

stagnant rather price structure and cost of production vary at different levels of time. Therefore, the Saudi think tank of business establishment makes a review of price structure at different levels of time(Altalhi, 2023; Foudeh, 2017; Jawadi&Ftiti, 2019; Llanos-Antczak, 2023; Mensi et al., 2018). In this regard, various economists and price analyst have endorsed their opinions in context with the KSA business scenario.The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Saudi Arabia was worth 1108.15 billion US dollars in 2022, according to official data from the World Bank. The GDP value of Saudi Arabia represents 0.49 percent of the world economy(Almutairi et al., 2023; *Saudi Arabia GDP*, 2023). Increased GDP in the Gulf Region is owed to the exploration of natural resources. These economic developments and globalization are growing emerging consumers; affecting their perception (tastes, values) and purchasing behavior (trends, preferences, habits), In terms of consumer behavior research, only a few topics have attracted the attention of academics, researchers, and professionals alike and have taken patronage behavior into account. According to (Karimet al., 2025; Roshidet al., 2025; Schallehn et al., 2019; Tanchangya et al., 2024) Customer needs are motivated by distinct product and service categories that are pertinent to their needs. Price, as seen from the perspective of the client, symbolizes the value that a person places on the item being traded. Marketers have been making claims. The customer is going to weigh up these promises against the price and decide whether it is worth paying (Prakash et al., 2021; Zeithaml et al., 1993). In assessing price, the customer is looking specifically at the expected benefits of the product as shown below:

Figure 1: Conceptual model of Emerging Trends and Socio-Cultural events.

Since 40% of people in the KSA are over 40, they have their own preferences, trends, and inclinations, purchasing habits. Two-thirds of Saudis prioritize quality over price (Ho, 2019; Market Research Report, 2023). The contemporary Saudi market caters to a new breed of clients that have their own unique preferences and usual options. Many researchers have suggested that the unique features of consumers have an impact on customer value, engaging customers positively influences customer value creation (Assad, 2008; Jassim& Al-Kawaz, 2022; Zhang et

al., 2017). The Gulf region has moved swiftly on the way to entering an age of mass consumption. Modern rational consumerism posits a controversy to social relations followed by traditional and religious values. The study of consumer culture has begun to take into implicate all areas of social life very seriously (Ahmadi, 2022; Alali et al., 2023; Karim, Hasan, Waaje, et al., 2024; Roshid et al., 2025). Hence, Saudi consumption pattern nowadays seems to be driven by the emulation of more developed predominately Western, economies. Marketers provide customers with a variety of products and services from various suppliers where they are able to make a comparison in terms of prices and quality and choose the best offer to them (Algumzi, 2022; Almohammadi & Abdulghaffar, 2022; Alqutub, 2023; Rahman, 2023). Market information is enhancing a one to one communication between the seller and the end buyer with round-the-clock customer service. Hence, this study is aimed to study the factors that influence the opportunities and constraints of consumerism in Saudi Arabia.

Based on the fact that economic diversified progress has been one of the strategic goals of the National Transformation Program that supports fulfilling the Saudi Vision 2030 by improving the market sector, and business environment to attract domestic and international investors, boosting small and medium enterprises and productive families in reaching their consumers and entering new markets. Such developments, in turn, will result in creating of new businesses and economic growth by commercial liquidity in the private sector, especially in the retail industry (Havrlant & Darandary, 2021; Moshashai et al., 2020; Roshid et al., 2024; Sarwar et al., 2021). This initiative will elevate the Kingdom's status as a global investment hub. Recent years witnessed spectacular Western consumerism, through manifestations of goods and services (luxury cars, modern technology, and Western fashion) in KSA; while consumerism has been grafted on widely still traditional cultural values, reaching consumers leads to long and parallel development of industrial production and mass consumption. As mentioned earlier, the kingdom has made it a priority to promote trade and investment. Industry and Commerce-related shopping data and available statistics illustrate a growing breed of clients cater to unique preferences and usual options (Karim et al., 2024; Roshid et al., 2024). The objective of this research is two-fold:

1. **To investigate how social and cultural dynamics influence the purchasing decisions of tech-savvy youth in Saudi Arabia, with a particular focus on the role of trust, price sensitivity, and cultural norms in shaping consumer behavior.**
2. **To examine the relationship between trend awareness and consumer pricing strategies in Saudi Arabia, specifically analyzing how awareness of counterfeit products and perceptions of extravagant consumption affect young consumers' propensity to follow trends and their sensitivity to pricing.**

By addressing these objectives, this research contributes to the existing body of knowledge on consumerism in Saudi Arabia by highlighting the **opportunities** that arise from the modernization of consumer behavior while also identifying the **constraints** posed by traditional values and socio-cultural influences. This dual perspective is essential for understanding the complexities of consumerism in the Kingdom, particularly in the context of the National Transformation Program and Saudi Vision 2030, which aim to diversify the economy and attract both domestic and international investments. Moreover, this study emphasizes the importance of understanding the distinct characteristics, motivations, and consumption styles of Saudi consumers. It seeks to answer critical questions regarding how socio-cultural factors—such as religion, traditions, family networks, and access to information—shape purchasing habits. Additionally, it aims to provide insights into the consumer trends that Saudi businesses should consider when marketing and producing goods. Ultimately, this research not only sheds light on the societal forces driving consumer behavior but also offers practical implications for retailers striving to meet the evolving needs of Saudi consumers.

Fundamentals of Buying Behavior

Customer or buyer needs, buying patterns, and motivations need to be defined from the managerial, economist, and social point of view. [Armstrong, \(1991\)](#) asserts that need arousal drives the purchase choice process, it begins with problem recognition. Consumer behavioral characteristics affect the benefits they want and how essential these

benefits are to them. The consumer determines they are 'in the market' for a product or service to meet a need or want. Bolton and Drew (1991) found that customers' characteristics are important when they assess value, but not when assessing service. Buying behavior is the process through which individual selects, purchase, and disposes of goods and services that satisfy their needs and wants (Kumar, 2010; Kotler & Keller, 2011). This integral part is based on customers' emotional and mental needs and behavioral responses. Leggett (2016) in her research article points out some of the trends in customer services provided in 2016. Points out that the following:

- a. Differentiated service deliveries real value
- b. Easy customer service
- c. Delivering effective customer service

To withstand the competitive products and services and increase exports, companies must be rational in understanding consumer behavior, and act. Analyzing customers' purchasing decisions, criteria, and demands according to marketing plans, has huge long-term benefits to the business organizations. Unique features of consumers have an impact on customer value, engaging customers positively influences customer value creation on demand (Zhang et al. 2017). Companies' success is bestowed by influencing consumers' purchasing decisions through advertising and promotion activities (Saleem & Abideen, 2011). Marketing specialists would prevail from studying customer behavior, perceptions, and attitudes.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Upcoming Patterns in Customer Action

Emerging trends in consumer behaviour reflect changes in society values, economy, and technology. The landscape of consumer behaviour is constantly altering. The growth of e-commerce and digitization have a major effect on consumer behaviour, according to studies. For example, Saudi Arabia's young, tech-savvy population and expanding internet penetration have fuelled the country's e-commerce platforms' meteoric rise (Assiri & Mirza, 2011; Zulfeeqar Alam & Elaasi, 2016). Furthermore, cellphones have made online buying incredibly accessible, leading to the rise of mobile commerce (Alzubaidi, 2018).

The rising profile of eco-friendly and morally sound purchasing practices is another noteworthy development. More and more, consumers are considering social and environmental impacts when making purchases. Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is gaining popularity among Saudi customers, who are increasingly interested in sustainable practices (Karim et al., 2023; Mohammed, 2020). Nonetheless, there is a lack of data on the precise ways in which these tendencies affect the purchasing habits of various Saudi market segments. Understanding how new technology like AI and AR affect Saudi consumer behaviour is an area where there is a lot of unanswered questions.

2.2 How Society and Culture Interact

The distinct socio-cultural environment of Saudi Arabia has a significant impact on consumer behaviour. The conservative character of Saudi society and the traditional values derived from Islamic principles influence consumer preferences and behaviours. Religious rituals, gender norms, and family dynamics all play important roles in this region's purchasing habits (Algumzi, 2022; Rambo et al., 2009).

Particularly important are gender dynamics. The Vision 2030 project and other recent social and political shifts have brought to a dramatic increase in women's agency and economic engagement (Altalhi, 2023; Havrlant&Darandary, 2021; Moshashai et al., 2020b, 2020a; Sarwar et al., 2021; *The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030*). Particularly in product categories where men have historically held sway, this change is likely to affect how people shop. There is still a lack of knowledge on how these changes are influencing consumer behaviour, especially when it comes to women's greater workforce involvement, despite the fact that there is study on the subject.

2.3 The Role of Socioeconomic Situation

Additionally, consumer behavior is influenced by economic variables including employment rates, income levels, and economic policies. By supporting industries like retail, entertainment, and tourism, the Vision 2030 plan hopes to diversify the economy away from its reliance on oil. The preferences and spending habits of consumers are likely to be affected by these developments (Donlagić&Moskalenko, 2020; Karim, Roshid, Dhar, et al., 2024; Rambo et al., 2009; Senan et al., 2018; Waaje et al., 2025). Nevertheless, there is a significant lack of research on how economic diversification affects consumer behaviour. It is crucial to comprehend how changes in economic policies and the emergence of new industries impact consumer preferences and spending patterns.

According to the McKinsey (2020-2021) Middle East Consumer Sentiment Survey reports, KSA lower-income tier consumers are getting more price sensitive, and overall, 50 percent of the respondents are cutting back on spending, trading down, and searing similar quality cheaper grocery options. Digital economy increased online users in KSA, 42% of these shoppers buy groceries online at least once a week. Eventually, traditional retailers are losing out on revenue growth opportunities. 3rdly, they prefer more healthy products and are socially sophisticated.

3. Research Methodology

The purpose of this study was to investigate the influence that a number of different factors have on consumer behavior by utilizing demographic information, correlation analysis, and multiple regression analysis. A quantitative technique that was based on survey research was utilized in order to collect primary data through the use of a structured questionnaire that was created using Google Forms. For the purpose of ensuring that respondents felt at ease and were more inclined to make truthful responses, the questionnaire was created to be an anonymous survey. Additionally, the questionnaire was divided into two pieces. The initial part of the survey consisted of collecting an assortment of demographic data, which included gender, age, income, education, and occupation. In the second segment, the focus was on the preferences of customers regarding their purchases and the factors that influence their purchasing behavior. Each facet consisted of two to four questions. The mall intercept approach was utilized at supermarkets, hypermarkets, and malls in order to ascertain the sample size. In order to explain the new trend of emerging KSA customers in the Saudi Arabian context, a convenient sampling method was carried out; this approach was chosen as it is the most appropriate for the time constraints of this study. The survey sample included 212 Saudi consumers. In particular, clients who were leaving these stores were contacted and interviewed using the

structured questionnaire in order to gain a better understanding of the trends that are forming among Saudi Arabian consumers. During the data collection process, both Makkah and Jeddah were visited.

There were questions on product authenticity checks, security features, payment methods, awareness of counterfeit goods, price concerns, trend-following behaviors, and purchasing habits included in the dataset. The dataset was comprised of survey results pertaining to many aspects of consumer behavior in Saudi Arabia. A correlation study was carried out in order to determine the strength of the associations between these variables as well as the direction in which they would go. Therefore, in order to shed light on the interrelationships between the variables, the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated for each and every pair of variables (Karmakar et al., 2022; Pareek & Mathur, 2022). The identification of potential predictors for the upcoming regression analysis was made easier by this preliminary analysis by providing the necessary information. A heatmap was used to show the correlation matrix, which provided a full visual representation of the correlations that exist between all of the variables (Silva et al., 2020).

Subsequently, multiple regression analysis was utilized in order to quantify the impact that the selected predictors had on the dependent variables, which were price sensitivity and trend awareness (Karimet al., 2025; Ramar, 2023; Roshid et al., 2024). There was a robust framework for understanding the components that influence consumer behavior in this setting, which was provided by the regression models, which comprised significant predictors as indicated by the correlation analysis. The findings of the study also highlighted the complex relationship that exists between the level of consumer awareness and the degree to which they are sensitive to price in the Saudi market. The findings shed light on the significant part that is played by product authenticity checks and security measures in the process of molding the perceptions and actions of consumers. The analysis also found that payment methods and awareness of phony brands have a major influence on price concerns and buying habits, which exemplifies the complexity of the decision-making processes that consumers engage in (Nahalková Tesárová & Křižanová, 2023). These discoveries have important repercussions for advertising professionals and governments who are working to encourage consumer behaviors that are both educated and secure.

4. Data Analysis and Implications

4.1.1 Demographic Information

In this section, descriptive statistics are employed to analyze the primary data pertaining to respondents' demographic information. The raw data is presented as percentages, encompassing variables such as age, gender, educational level, monthly income, and occupation.

Table 1: Demographic Information

Age	Respondents in Number	Respondents in Percentage
<i>18 - 24</i>	93	43.87
<i>25 - 40</i>	75	35.38
<i>41 - 55</i>	30	14.15
<i>50 -60</i>	14	6.60
Gender	Respondents in Number	Respondents in Percentage
<i>Male</i>	136	64.15
<i>Female</i>	76	35.85
Educational level	Respondents in Number	Respondents in Percentage
<i>Post Graduate Degree</i>	32	15.09
<i>Graduate Degree</i>	93	43.87
<i>Diploma</i>	72	33.96
<i>Ph.D</i>	15	7.08
Monthly Income	Respondents in Number	Respondents in Percentage
<i>Less than SR 4000</i>	80	37.74
<i>SR 4000 - SR 8000</i>	87	41.04
<i>SR 8000 – SR 10000</i>	30	14.15
<i>Above SR 10000</i>	15	7.08
Occupation	Respondents in Number	Respondents in Percentage
<i>Professional</i>	47	22.17
<i>Public Sector</i>	62	29.25
<i>Private Sector</i>	66	31.13

<i>Other Jobs</i>	37	17.45
-------------------	----	-------

The demographic information table shows that the youngest participants were 18–24 years old (43.87%), followed by those in the 25–40 age range (35.38%), those in the 41–55 age range (14.15%), and those in the 50–60 age range (6.60%). There were fewer women than men among the respondents (35.85% vs. 64.15 percent). A total of 43.87 percent of respondents held a master's degree or above, 15.09 percent a post-graduate degree, 33.96 percent a diploma, and 7.08% a doctorate. Respondents' monthly income was likewise divided into four categories in the study. Nearly half of the respondents (41.04%) said their income was between SR 4000 and SR 8000. The next highest percentage was 37.34%, followed by 14.15% for SR 8000 to SR 10,000, and a lesser percentage of 7.08% for SR 10,000 or more. When broken down by profession, the survey found that 31.13 percent of respondents worked in the private sector, 29.25 percent in the public sector, 22.17% as professionals, and 17.45 percent in some other occupation. Based on this demographic profile, it seems that most of the respondents were young people, mostly men, with a fair amount of college degrees and middle-class salaries. A pertinent backdrop for evaluating consumer behavior patterns in Makkah and Jeddah supermarkets, hypermarkets, and malls is provided by the fact that most participants were employed in the private sector.

4.1.2 Correlation Insights

A correlation study was conducted with the purpose of determining the strength and direction of the links that exist between the various variables that pertain to consumer behavior. In order to determine the extent to which the variables are related to one another, we computed the Pearson correlation coefficient for each and every pair of variables. A thorough picture of these associations was offered by the visualization of the correlation matrix through the use of a heatmap. As a result, important correlations were highlighted, which informed further regression studies. Several variables were found to have substantial positive relationships with trend awareness, including awareness of false brands (0.475), confidence in an extravagant consumption era (0.452), price concern (0.439), and expenditure on social and religious activities (0.438). These findings were derived from the correlation analysis which showed key conclusions. Additionally, there were significant associations found between price sensitivity and the following: awareness of phony brands (0.474), awareness of trends (0.439), belief in an era of excessive consumption (0.381), and spending on social and religious activities (0.369).

According to these connections, consumers who are aware of fake brands, who believe that we are living in an era of excessive consumption, and who are concerned about costs are more likely to follow trends and be sensitive to fluctuations in price. A more in-depth investigation using regression models was made possible as a result of this preliminary analysis.

Figure 2: Correlation Insights of all variables

4.1.3 Trend Awareness Predictors

Quantifying the influence of a number of different factors on the propensity of consumers to follow trends was the objective of the multiple regression analysis for trend awareness. Through the use of correlation analysis, the dependent variable, which was referred to as "Fond of following trends to visible goods and habits in social family programs," was studied in comparison to the independent factors selected. A value of 0.416 was found for the R-squared component of the regression model after it was fitted using the ordinary least squares (OLS) method. It can be deduced from this that the model is capable of explaining around 41.6% of the amount of variation in trend

awareness. A number of factors were found to be significant predictors ($p < 0.05$), including belief in an extravagant spending era, awareness of bogus brands, concern regarding price, and various ways of payment.

Figure 3: Trend Awareness Predictions

Particularly, the awareness of bogus brands had a substantial beneficial impact on trend awareness (coefficient: 0.1983, p-value: 0.003). This was the case. Based on this research, it appears that consumers who are aware of the existence of counterfeit products are more likely to purchase fashionable items. Another factor that had a positive relationship on trend awareness was the belief in an extravagant consumption era (coefficient: 0.1554, p-value: 0.004). This suggests that customers who view their era to be one of excessive consumption are more aware of trends. Additionally, price concern (coefficient: 0.1345, p-value: 0.018) and various means of payment (coefficient: 0.1877, p-value: 0.002) were found to be significant predictors, indicating the significance that financial considerations and payment flexibility have in driving behavior that follows trends. Marketers who want to reach consumer segments that are aware of trends absolutely need to have these insights. One way to effectively appeal to this demographic is to place an emphasis on the genuineness of the products and to make use of flexible payment alternatives.

4.1.4 Price Sensitivity Predictors

Understanding the elements that influence customers' primary worry about pricing was the primary focus of the regression analysis for price sensitivity. When compared to a group of independent factors that were discovered by correlation analysis, the dependent variable, which was "Price is my primary concern," was also investigated. An R-squared value of 0.327 was obtained using the regression model, which indicates that the model is capable of

explaining roughly 32.7% of the differences in price sensitivity. A number of factors were shown to be significant predictors ($p < 0.05$), including the awareness of fake brands, the awareness of trends, the belief in an era of excessive consumption, and the spending on attending social and religious activities.

Figure 4: Price Sensitivity Predictions

The most significant predictor was the awareness of imitation brands, with a coefficient of 0.3713 and a p-value of less than 0.001. This indicates that consumers who are particularly attentive about counterfeit items are also extremely sensitive to pricing. Those who are concerned about pricing are also those who follow trends, as indicated by the fact that trend awareness had a positive impact on price sensitivity (coefficient: 0.1985, p-value: 0.020). Spending on social and religious events (coefficient: 0.1825, p-value: 0.048) and belief in an extravagant consumption era (coefficient: 0.1356, p-value: 0.046) were significant predictors, highlighting the importance of societal and cultural influences on price sensitivity. Both of these were significant predictors. In order to attract customers that are price-conscious, it is recommended that marketers place an emphasis on promoting the value and authenticity of their products and services. To further assist in tailoring marketing strategies to better match the requirements of consumers, it is helpful to have a grasp of the cultural and societal circumstances that influence price sensitivity.

4.2 Implications for Advertising and Interaction with Customers

The insights that were obtained from the correlation and regression studies give useful implications for marketing strategies and the involvement of consumers. By gaining an understanding of the significant relationship that exists between the awareness of fake brands and both trend awareness and price sensitivity, one can better appreciate the significance of product authenticity in the decision-making process of consumers. By ensuring that their products are regarded as genuine and by informing consumers about the authenticity measures that are in place, marketers have the opportunity to capitalize on this concept. As a result of the favorable influence that believing in an extravagant consumption era has on both trend awareness and price sensitivity, it is suggested that marketing messaging should resonate with customers' perceptions of modern consumption patterns. By highlighting products that match with these preconceptions, it is possible to effectively engage consumers who are price-sensitive and knowledgeable of contemporary trends.

In addition, the fact that price concerns and payment flexibility play a role in driving trend awareness highlights the importance of pricing strategies that provide both value and ease. It is possible to attract customers who place a high value on pricing and are likely to follow trends by providing them with promotional offers, discounts, and different payment choices. A thorough understanding of the primary drivers of consumer behaviors is provided by these studies, which can be utilized to design targeted marketing strategies and boost consumer engagement in the Saudi Arabian market. In conclusion, these analyses provide a comprehensive summary of the findings.

5. Discussion

This section focuses on the factors that influence Saudi shoppers' behavior and their attitudes towards consumerism. The study highlights the importance of understanding these factors in order to cater to the needs and preferences of the Saudi consumer market. The sources that address this theme explore how various aspects of consumer culture, such as values, beliefs, norms, lifestyles, and identities, shape the preferences and choices of Saudi customers. The middle-class youth populations of this country's customers are the backbone in the change and growth of new emerging and buying customer in KSA. Consumers of aged between 0 and 24 estimated one third of the kingdom's population (Almutairi et al., 2023), positioning them as pivotal drivers of change in the emerging consumer landscape.

As appeared in the analysis of the trust factor, Saudi consumers prefer traditional purchasing methods and feel partially secure when using credit cards or other economic modalities for payment (cash, mobile phone). This indicates that there is a level of apprehension among Saudi consumers when it comes to online transactions and non-traditional payment methods. Trust is identified as a crucial factor influencing the shopping behavior of Saudi consumers. They prioritize the authenticity of shops and products, indicating that they value trustworthiness and reliability in their purchasing decisions. Saudi consumers actively check for the trustworthiness and goodwill of the stores they engage with, suggesting that they seek reassurance before making a purchase. They agree that Security features used by the stores to protect credit card details and personal information are acceptable. Secure and various payment methods and receipt increased their trust in the stores, and they are also aware of fake products. If trust is achieved; risk is most likely to decline and shoppers are comfortable with the shop. This awareness suggests that Saudi consumers are cautious and vigilant when making purchasing decisions, as they strive to avoid counterfeit or low-quality products. This is consistent with (Assiri & Mirza, 2011; Karmakar et al., 2023), in which the study discovered that online trust is crucial for customers, for fostering positive consumer behavior, indicating that retailers must cultivate trusting relationships with customers. In a global context, similar trends have been

observed in markets like China, where consumers are increasingly cautious about online shopping due to concerns over trust and product authenticity. Companies like Alibaba have successfully addressed these concerns by implementing robust buyer protection policies and transparent seller ratings, which enhance trust and encourage online transactions (Kwak et al., (2019).

Consumer behavior is favorably impacted by the perceived trust. In regard to the price factor, Saudi customers consider paying if they get the product or service at a low price if the price is reasonable for them. The GDP value of Saudi Arabia represents 0.49 percent of the world economy (*Saudi Arabia GDP*, 2023). Market growth, financial interdependence, and product diversity play a key role in purchasing. Two third of Saudis are prioritizing quality over price (Altalhi, 2023). Hence, Saudi is a tradition-directed society, they prefer spending on social family programs as a Bandwagon effect. Customers need to build up the self-esteem of recognition from visualizing wealth and assets, viz (Cars, lands, houses) as a Bandwagon effect: demand increases due to the fact that others are consuming the product (i.e. fashion). b) The snob effect occurs when demand falls because others are consuming a certain product. c) Veblen effect: demand increases when the price is higher rather than lower (Leibenstein, 1950). In contrast, markets in Europe and North America have seen a rise in "value-driven" consumers who seek quality products at competitive prices (Williamson, 2010; Lou et al., 2022). For example, brands like Uniqlo and Zara have thrived by offering high-quality apparel at accessible price points, effectively catering to consumers who are willing to pay more for quality but still seek reasonable pricing (Kumar, 2019).

Though globalisation and changes in the international environment have an impact on Saudi people, even though Islam plays a significant role in the country's daily lives, Saudis respond to modernization by acquiring and consuming goods to elevate their social status and to publicly display their ability to buy luxury goods (Abdellatif et al., 2018; Al-Hyari et al., 2012). Indeed, younger consumers tend to emulate Western consumer attitudes and this is reflected in demand for a wide range of products in KSA. In addition, Saudi customers were neutral regarding the social influence on their purchasing behavior in terms of social media and the opinions of their families and people. This is due to the increased awareness of the new generation of society where they become more realized of the impact of social media advertising that may not be true and just to market a product or service. In comparison, markets in Southeast Asia exhibit similar trends, where young consumers are also navigating the balance between traditional values and modern consumerism. For instance, in Indonesia, brands like Go-Jek have successfully integrated local cultural elements into their marketing strategies while embracing modern technology, thereby appealing to the younger demographic (Muhammad, 2023).

The consumers are not brand maniacs; they can't afford to live in the state of hibernation. KSA customers are aware of new growing trends as well as their basic needs that compel them to identify the right choice of product. They prefer to purchase their desired brands in stores with lower prices. The KSA business think tank has to readjust, remodel and reshuffle its products, pack size, pricing, packaging and above all quality control. Urban modern consumers are more exposed to high quality particular electronic brands and westernized consumption for warranty and guaranty. This finding supports the study conducted by (Al Salamin et al., 2015), which found that although young people are interested in buying branded goods, their purchasing intentions are negatively impacted by price. Ramadan or Eid (al Fitr and al Adha) has turned into a consumer fest as well, it has become a season of shopping and huge consumption. Historically, hospitality is an elaborate ritual presided over and controlled by the host. Like all rituals, it follows exacting rules. Nowadays, the Influx of religious tourists particularly on the religious occasion of Hajj and Umrah is the second largest contribution to Saudi Arabia's GDP. This seasonal consumer behavior mirrors trends in other regions, such as the Christmas shopping season in Western countries, where consumers engage in heightened purchasing activity driven by cultural and religious festivities (Belk et al., 1993).

Retailers globally, like Flipkart, Amazon, eBay, and Myntra can take advantage of sales opportunities during peak shopping seasons. capitalize on these seasonal trends through targeted marketing campaigns and special promotions, effectively driving sales during peak shopping (Sidra et al., 2023). In Saudi Arabia, local retailers can similarly leverage cultural events to boost sales by offering tailored promotions and enhancing the shopping experience during these times.

Taking into account the data exhibited by KSA Government about 12 million tourists pay visits to KSA per year.

Table 2:Inbound Tourist Trips by Purpose of Visit and Quarter

Purpose of Visit	First Quarter	Second Quarter	Third Quarter	Fourth Quarter (E)	Total	Market Share %
Religious	490974	706492	1574652	2094808	4867387	44.9 %

Source: (Institute for Hajj and Umrah Research, 2022)

In the discussion of the convenience factor, the study has shown that a new category of customers is no longer deluded by discounts, deals, and offers while shopping. In most cases, they are in search of their choice of commodity taking into view their basic need and their purchasing power as well. They prefer to shop for grocery items on instant cash payment rather than credit, maintaining a monthly record. But, monthly shopping for regular usage and consumption still presents time-saving. This result aligns with the study conducted by (Yusuf, 2016; ZulfequarAlam & Elaasi, 2016), who examined the relative ease of traditional and online grocery buying and discovered that, in comparison to traditional shopping, online grocery shopping lacks confidence qualities. Moreover, the majority of Saudi customers are satisfied with purchasing and services. If they are content with their shopping experience they will buy products again from the same shop if they are satisfied with it. Satisfaction can seriously affect buying behavior. Accessing desired information of the best quality keeps consumers motivated to buy, and the high-cost price will negatively impact buying from the same shop compared to friends, colleagues, and known ones. Accordingly, the sources agree that consumerism is a complex and dynamic phenomenon that requires a multidimensional approach to understand its impact on Saudi society. The overall results prove that the respondents have perceived rational shopping positively. This clearly shows the large growth of trade and industry in Saudi Arabia in light of Saudi Vision 2030.

6. Recommendations

The results of this paper will help the government, firms, and vendors to better understand KSA shoppers. The research also helps leaders to adopt and develop a better purchasing environment with a technological competitive advantage for traditional vendors and consumers. Saudi companies should concentrate on setting effective marketing and sales strategies to draw clients. Companies or firms should find more methods to reach their targeted customers and promote their branding. Vendor, retailers should offer customers more product and pricing options to fulfill diverse demands. This study has come forward to recommend several recommendations for the industry. Among such recommendations: to increase consumer confidence, reliance, and retention companies must develop strong privacy policies. Hence, businesses in Saudi Arabia, need to improve their transactions systems, such as securing financial and personal information. Additionally, customers must be provided with a good range of quality customer service, to enhance usability and the shopping process. Marketers should provide various facilities to create positive

attitudes among Saudi customers. They have to encourage them to shop by providing the required information, more choices, deals, and discounts for purchasing. These concerns will act as a motivation to customers for shopping.

7. Conclusion

The findings support the need for improved product and service growth in terms of quality, packaging, and price that meet the demands of consumers. Trust and authenticity are essential in both the product and the marketplace; when customers' perceptions correspond with this element, they are more inclined to purchase. Saudi clients appear to be interested in obtaining and receiving items or services at a fair price. While buying, Saudi customers are occasionally impacted by social factors. They all agree that they spend a lot of money on social and religious activities due to peer pressure, but not necessarily on branded things. Moreover, Nowadays the limited traditional offer of salable consumer commodities can't fix the consumers. Registered record keeping on credits is no longer a familiar style. Most consumers are satisfied with the marketing setup and proper market information about products and services. The research findings are aligned with SDG's Goal 12: Responsible Consumption and Production, emphasizes the importance of quality, trust, and consumer awareness while linking these concepts to sustainable practices. These findings will provide knowledge of the general requisites of consumers, and help investors and business analysts in the region by improving their plans and setting their marketing strategies. To navigate the Saudi Arabian market, investors should be dynamic with new commodities, pricing, and packaging; assessing the increasing business value; and elasticity of demand and, prices are the way. Conducting research with social listening tactics on emerging trends including real-time data analytics, mobile research, artificial intelligence, online communities, and cross-channel integration is important. Therefore, it has rightly been stated that awareness of the terms and conditions of a saleable commodity-alone can defend the cause of different categories of buyers. According to the Consumer Protection Act of Saudi Arabia, a contract comes into formation only when the offer as mentioned by the seller is accepted by the buyer but any prior concealment of the constituents and side effects of the product is thus subject to violation of the original terms and conditions as mentioned in Consumer Protection Act of KSA.

Reference

- Abdellatif, M., Auf, A., Meddour, H., Saoula, O., Halim, A., & Majid, A. (2018). Consumer buying behaviour: the roles of price, motivation, perceived culture importance, and religious orientation. In *www.jbrmr.com A Journal of the Academy of Business and Retail Management* (Vol. 12). ABRM. www.jbrmr.com
- Ahmadi, T. Al. (2022). An Analysis of the Economic Value of Substances of Abuse Seized in Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Forensic Sciences*, 7(4), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.23880/ijfsc-16000284>
- Al Salamin, H., Al-Baqshi, J., Al Rasasi, M., & Al Salem, H. (2015). Journal of Marketing and Consumer Research www.iiste.org ISSN. In *An International Peer-reviewed Journal* (Vol. 18). www.iiste.org

- Alali, B. M., Mosbah, E. B., & Ali, A. (2023). Consumer decision-making and segmentation of dates market in Saudi Arabia. *Italian Journal of Food Science*, 35(3), 141–154. <https://doi.org/10.15586/IJFS.V35I3.2314>
- Algumzi, A. (2022). Factors Influencing Saudi Young Female Consumers' Luxury Fashion in Saudi Arabia: Predeterminants of Culture and Lifestyles in Neom City. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 15(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/JRFM15070274>
- Al-Hyari, K., Alnsour, M., Al-Weshah, G., & Haffar, M. (2012). Religious beliefs and consumer behaviour: From loyalty to boycotts. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 3(2), 155–174. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17590831211232564>
- Almohammadi, H. G., & Abdulghaffar, N. A. (2022). The Influencing Factors of Consumers' Purchase Intention toward Green Products: A Case of Consumers in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 15(4), 136. <https://doi.org/10.5539/JSD.V15N4P136>
- Almutairi, K. , Alahmadi, R., Almutairi, K., & Alahmadi, R. (2023). Assessing the Impact of the Recent Unprecedented World Events on the Economic and Environmental Conditions of Saudi Arabia. *Sustainability*, 15(2), 1610–1610. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU15021610>
- Alqutub, K. (2023). Factors Influencing Impulse Buying Behavior Among Young Male Consumers in Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 15(2), 36. <https://doi.org/10.5539/IJMS.V15N2P36>
- Altalhi, H. (2023). Transitioning Away from an Oil-based Economy through Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030. *Humanities and Management Sciences - Scientific Journal of King Faisal University*, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.37575/H/MNG/220052>
- Alzubaidi, H. (2018). *Factors Affecting Consumers' Pro-environmental Behaviours in Saudi Arabia*. 303–314. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-75013-2_23
- Armstrong, J. S. (1991). Prediction of consumer behavior by experts and novices. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 18(2), 251-256. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1086/209257>
- Assad, S. W. (2008). The rise of consumerism in Saudi Arabian society. *International Journal of Commerce and Management*, 17(1–2), 73–104. <https://doi.org/10.1108/10569210710774767>
- Assiri, A. S., & Mirza, A. A. (2011). Causes of Mistrust and the Most Effective Authentication Tools for Improving Saudi Arabian Consumers' Willingness to Participate in E-commerce. *Proceedings on the International Conference on Internet Computing (ICOMP)*. www.nuqudy.com
- Bolton, R. N., & Drew, J. H. (1991). A multistage model of customers' assessments of service quality and value. *Journal of consumer research*, 17(4), 375-384. <https://doi.org/10.1086/208564>
- Belk, R. W., & Bryce, W. (1993). Christmas shopping scenes: from modern miracle to postmodern mall. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 10(3), 277-296.
- Donlagić, A., & Moskalenko, B. A. (2020). The Impact Of FDI Inflow On The Environment: A Case Of The Baltic-Black Sea Region Countries. *SocioEconomic Challenges*, 4(4), 151–159. [https://doi.org/10.21272/SEC.4\(4\).151-159.2020](https://doi.org/10.21272/SEC.4(4).151-159.2020)

- Foudeh, M. (2017). The Long Run Effects of Oil Prices on Economic Growth: The Case of Saudi Arabia. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*.
- Havrlant, D., & Darandary, A. (2021). *Economic Diversification under Saudi Vision 2030*. <https://doi.org/10.30573/KS--2021-DP06>
- Ho, M. (2019). *Saudi Arabia: Consumer Market Characteristics and Current Developments* /. HKTDC Research. <https://research.hktdc.com/en/article/MzQ1OTAzNzE2>
- Institute for Hajj and Umrah Research*. (2022). Umm Al-Qura University. <https://uqu.edu.sa/en/hajj>
- Jassim, O. A. L., & Al-Kawaz, S. M. (2022). Economic measurement of the impact of some macroeconomic variables on the foreign trade of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia for the period (1990-2019). *Tikrit Journal of Administrative and Economic Sciences*, 18(58, 1), 155–173. <https://doi.org/10.25130/TJAES.18.58.1.9>
- Jawadi, F., & Ftiti, Z. (2019). Oil price collapse and challenges to economic transformation of Saudi Arabia: A time-series analysis. *Energy Economics*, 80, 12–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENECO.2018.12.003>
- Karim, R., Hasan, Md. M., Waaje, A., Yesmin, Mst. S. H., & Roshid, Md. M. (2024). Financial Performance of Bangladeshi Listed Commercial Banks: A Generation-based Analysis. *International Journal of Finance & Banking Studies (2147-4486)*, 12(4), 46–56. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijfbs.v12i4.3170>
- Karim, R., Roshid, M. M., & Waaje, A. (2024). Circular economy and supply chain sustainability. In *Strategic Innovations for Dynamic Supply Chains*. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-3575-8.ch001>
- Karim, R., Roshid, M. M., & Waaje, A. (2025). Does the Firm Size Matter for Financial Performance? — Evidence from the Financial Sector of a South Asian Emerging Economy. *EMIDWORLD 2nd International Congress on Economics Public Finance Business & Social Sciences*, 461–474.
- Karim, R., Roshid, Md. M., Dhar, B. K., Nahiduzzaman, Md., & Kuri, B. C. (2024). Audit Committee Characteristics and Sustainable Firms' Performance: Evidence From the Financial Sector in Bangladesh. *Business Strategy & Development*, 7(4). <https://doi.org/10.1002/bsd2.70059>
- Karim, R., Roshid, Md. M., Shamme, F. B., & Hasan, Md. M. (2023). Non-performing Loans and Bank Profitability: Evidence from Bangladesh. *International Journal of Finance & Banking Studies (2147-4486)*, 11(4), 95–102. <https://doi.org/10.20525/ijfbs.v11i4.2314>
- Karim, R., Waaje, A., Roshid, Md. M., & Yeamin, Md. B. (2025). Turning the Waste Into Wealth: Progressing Toward Global Sustainability Through the Circular Economy in Waste Management. In R. Sucheran (Ed.), *Sustainable Waste Management in the Tourism and Hospitality Sectors* (pp. 507–552). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-6110-8.ch019>

- Karmakar, A., Hossain Khan, Z., Roshid, M., HoshainYesmin, S., & Bashar Shamme, F. (2023). Consumer Learning and Split-Brain Theory: Potential Usage in an Advertisement. *International Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Sciences*, 11(3), 168–176. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.ijefm.20231103.21>
- Karmakar, A., Khan. Ziarat Hossain, Roshid, Md. M., Shamme, F. B., & Rahman, Md. A. (2022). A Study of Farmers Direct Marketing: Assessing the Factors for the Home to Land Approach. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 14(22), 45–56. <https://doi.org/10.7176/ejbm/14-22-05>
- Kwak, J., Zhang, Y., & Yu, J. (2019). Legitimacy building and e-commerce platform development in China: The experience of Alibaba. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 139, 115-124.
- Kotler, P. & Keller, K. (2011) “Marketing Management”(14th edition), London: Pearson Education
- Kumar, P. (2010) “Marketing of Hospitality & Tourism Services” Tata McGraw-Hill Education
- Kumar, R. (2019). Retail Management. *Human Resource Management*, 132, 146.
- Leggett, K. (2016). Trends 2016: The Future of Customer Service. URL: <https://www.forrester.com/report/Trends-2016-The-Future-Of-Customer-Service/RES61372>
- Leibenstein, H. (1950). Bandwagon, Snob, and Veblen Effects in the Theory of Consumers’ Demand. In *Source: The Quarterly Journal of Economics* (Vol. 64, Issue 2).
- Llanos-Antczak, A. (2023). Perspectives of Shifting From Oil-Based Economy to Knowledge-Based Economy in Saudi Arabia. *Journal for Perspectives of Economic Political and Social Integration*, 28(2), 7–40. <https://doi.org/10.18290/PEPSI-2022-0006>
- Lou, X., Chi, T., Janke, J., & Desch, G. (2022). How do perceived value and risk affect purchase intention toward second-hand luxury goods? An empirical study of US consumers. *Sustainability*, 14(18), 11730.
- Market Research Report. (2023). *Saudi Arabia: Consumer Profile*. Euromonitor. <https://www.euromonitor.com/saudi-arabia-consumer-profile/report>
- Mensi, W., Hussain Shahzad, S. J., Hammoudeh, S., & Al-Yahyaee, K. H. (2018). Asymmetric impacts of public and private investments on the non-oil GDP of Saudi Arabia. *International Economics*, 156, 15–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.INTECO.2017.10.003>
- Mohammed, A. A. (2020). What motivates consumers to purchase organic food in an emerging market? An empirical study from Saudi Arabia. *British Food Journal*, 123(5), 1758–1775. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BFJ-07-2020-0599>
- Moshashai, D., Leber, A. M., & Savage, J. D. (2020a). Saudi Arabia plans for its economic future: Vision 2030, the National Transformation Plan and Saudi fiscal reform. *British Journal of Middle Eastern Studies*, 47(3), 381–401. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13530194.2018.1500269>

Moshashai, D., Leber, A. M., & Savage, J. D. (2020b). Saudi Arabia plans for its economic future: Vision 2030, the National Transformation Plan and Saudi fiscal reform. *British Journal of Middle Eastern Studies*, 47(3), 381–401. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13530194.2018.1500269>

Muhammad Ryan, S. (2023). THE INFLUENCE OF CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE, CUSTOMER SATISFACTION & CUSTOMER LOYALTY TOWARDS BRAND POWER (STUDY ON GO-RIDE SERVICE BY GOJEK IN BANDAR LAMPUNG).

NahalkováTesárová, E., &Križanová, A. (2023). The use regression and correlation analysis in generational stratification and consumer behaviour. *13th International Scientific Conference "Business and Management 2023."* <https://doi.org/10.3846/BM.2023.949>

Pareek, A., & Mathur, N. (2022). A Study to Analysis and Identify the Behavioral Relationship between the Attitude and Factor Affecting Consumer towards Green Behavior. *International Journal on Recent Trends in Business and Tourism (IJRTBT)*, 6(3), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.31674/IJRTBT.2022.V06I03.001>

Prakash, C., Yadav, R., &Kadyan, S. (2021). Effect of the price drop on customer's perceived evaluation across selected product categories. *Journal of Revenue and Pricing Management*, 20(2), 204–210. <https://doi.org/10.1057/S41272-021-00301-6>

Rahman, M. N. (2023). Analytical study of correlation between retail store image and shopping behaviour of Saudi Arabian consumers. *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, 10(3), 123–132. [https://doi.org/10.9770/JESI.2023.10.3\(9\)](https://doi.org/10.9770/JESI.2023.10.3(9))

Ramar, N. (2023). Multiple Regression Analysis Based Consumer Behavior Prediction for Marketing Multiple Regression Analysis Based Consumer Behavior Prediction for Marketing. *Shanlax International Journal of Management*, 10(3), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.34293/MANAGEMENT.V10I3.5285>

Rambo, K., Liu, K., & Nakata, K. (2009). The socio-cultural factors influencing online female consumers in Saudi Arabia: An organisational semiotics perspective. *Proceedings - 12th IEEE International Conference on Computational Science and Engineering, CSE 2009*, 4, 633–638. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CSE.2009.443>

Roshid, M. M., Karim, R., &Waaje, A. (2025). Synergizing Circular Economy and H2H Marketing: A Sustainable Approach to Human-Centric Business. *EMIDWORLD 2nd International Congress on Economics Public Finance Business & Social Sciences*, 767–783. www.emidworld.com

Roshid, M. M., Waaje, A., & Karim, R. (2025). Industry 6.0 as an Emerging Field of Research: A Systematic and Bibliometric Analysis. *EMIDWORLD 2nd International Congress on Economics Public Finance Business & Social Sciences*, 784–802.

Roshid, M. M., Waaje, A., Meem, T. N., & Sarkar, A. (2024). Logistics 4.0: A Comprehensive Literature Review of Technological Integration, Challenges, and Future Prospects of Implementation of Industry 4.0 Technologies. *International Journal of Technology, Knowledge and Society*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.18848/1832-3669/CGP/v20i01/65-85>

[AMYtAIY5QIY6gIYjAMYjwHYAQFI3AdQlwVYlwVwAXgAkAEAmAEAoAEAqgEAuAEDyAEA-AEB-AECmAIBoAIRqAIUmAMRugYGCAEQARgLkgcBMAHAA&sclient=gws-wiz-serp](#)

Waaje, A., Karim, R., Roshid, Md. M., & Meem, T. N. (2025). Minimizing Waste in the Hospitality Industry: The Opportunities and Challenges of Lean Tourism. In R. Sucheran (Ed.), *Sustainable Waste Management in the Tourism and Hospitality Sectors* (pp. 125–166). IGI Global.

<https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-6110-8.ch006>

Williamson, P. J. (2010). Cost innovation: preparing for a ‘value-for-money’ revolution. *Long Range Planning*, 43(2-3), 343-353.

Yusuf, N. (2016). Increased Labor Productivity, Stronger Business Environment-Transforming the Economy, Saudi Arabia. *The International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 6(8), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/V6-I8/2250>

Zeithaml, V. A., Berry, L. L., & Parasuraman, A. (1993). The Nature and Determinants of Customer Expectations of Service. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 21(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0092070393211001>

Zhang, M., Guo, L., Hu, M., & Liu, W. (2017). Influence of customer engagement with company social networks on stickiness: Mediating effect of customer value creation. *International Journal of Information Management*, 37(3), 229–240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2016.04.010>

ZulfearquarAlam, M., &Elaasi, S. A. (2016). A Study on Consumer Perception towards E-Shopping in KSA. *International Journal of Biometrics*, 11(7), 202. <https://doi.org/10.5539/IJBM.V11N7P202>